

THE ROLE AND DIFFERENCES OF GENDER IN ATTITUDE TO LEARNING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract: This article actively discusses the issue of gender education and upbringing in the modern education system. Due to the fact that single-sex schools do not exist in Uzbekistan, as in a number of countries such as Western Europe and the United States, psychologists and sociologists, by conducting a series of experiments and researches in different schools of gender education, have determined the positive and negative aspects of this form of education. It is stated that conclusions have been made about the parties.

Key words: sociologist, physiological, psychological, gender approach, cortex, concept.

Introduction.

According to these conclusions, same-sex students at school were less prone to social pressure: boys were more self-confident, and girls were able to develop leadership qualities faster. The article provides information on the discussion of the training of boys who are students of the naval school. It is said that teachers working in such educational institutions should study the main aspects of physiological and psychological development of boys so that the educational process will be successful. It is known that the right hemisphere of boys is more developed than that of girls, so they are oriented faster in space and more actively perform tasks related to immediate achievement of the goal. Boys perform better on standardized tests, and subjects like math, physics, chemistry, and geography are more useful to them than girls.

Typical behaviors for boys are boisterous, active, observant, and engaging in a variety of tasks that require experience. At different age levels, they are more likely to display character traits such as leadership qualities and competitiveness in classroom and extracurricular activities. Gender education at school is based on the following principles.

Democratic.

With this approach to education, boys have equal rights to education and participation in the community life of the school; they interact not against each other, but on the basis of partnership;

Natural compatibility. Recognizing the individual equality of boys does not mean denying biological and physiological characteristics and differences in their life activities. Recognizing these differences requires different forms of teaching, methods and tools to help students realize their full potential as representatives of their gender in the classroom and extracurricular activities. Meeting the demands of the times. The unity of actions of the teacher and the student's parents with the gender approach to education is especially relevant.

If we consider the gender approach in teaching foreign languages, in particular, English, the gender factor has a multifaceted effect on the characteristics of thinking,

perception, interpretation and practical use of the received information, at different stages. determines the use of certain mental strategies in the cognitive, emotional and motivational domains of students. Acquisition of communication skills in the main types of speech activities performed by students in foreign language classes (speaking, listening, reading, writing) differs from teaching girls.

There are gender characteristics in the acquisition and use of language units related to the main types of speech activity (phonetics, vocabulary, grammar). Gender specificity is observed in mastering the pronunciation of sounds in English, in mastering lexical units and grammatical forms and categories intended for study at school. An analysis of the types of functional asymmetry and the characteristics of interhemispheric interaction is presented in the works of well-known local neuropsychologists E. A. Simernitskaya, E. D. Khomskaya and others.

High nervous activity of students in learning a foreign language occurs in the weakest and relatively easily damaged part of the second signal system. At the same time, the attention of students decreases and the act of memorization is stopped. In this regard, it should be remembered that "a teacher who wants to firmly inculcate something in the child's memory must ensure that as many senses as possible - eyes, ears, sound, muscle movement - are involved in this action. need and memorize it in this way.

Such different methodological methods significantly increase the performance of students, because they involve other analyzers, new, non-fatiguing areas of the cerebral cortex and change the nature of stimuli." The use of gender tests in teaching English meets modern principles. Reader the concept of communicative teaching of a foreign language culture that is oriented towards the individual dominates the material motives for boys. have

The teacher offers students various thematic texts that talk about the military component, biographies of famous English commanders, military affairs, inventions in world science. In order to develop monologue, it is preferable for students to perform tasks that require observation of language. Boys often find themselves in situations that require them to display strength, independence, power, and competition—qualities that do not fit the concept of femininity. Therefore, they are more willing to perform creative tasks that require imagination and observation.

It should also be noted that their speech is less expressive, there are very few "embellished" adjectives in their speech. When using colors in speech, they use the traditional spectrum, despite the fact that they know many shades. The teacher should make sure that the boys try to use the minimum necessary vocabulary in their statements. An emotionally neutral style is more characteristic of their speech behavior, they avoid external manifestations of emotionality, such as pleasure, impatience, and excessive politeness. For occasional use, new speech patterns are quickly understood but quickly forgotten.

Boys have a much higher passive vocabulary, and they quickly recognize words that are rarely used in the text, so when teaching vocabulary, it is useful to organize visual information into columns, create clusters together with students, as well as abstract it is recommended to offer tasks that involve thinking. . Boys need high-paced, varied activities and information-rich lessons. The use of different forms and methods of work gives positive results. The teacher can invite students to form clusters by themselves to combine lexical material and present them in groups or pairs.

Group 1.

To study vocabulary and speech, it is necessary to transfer the lexical and grammatical material from the general to the specific using the "Fields of Science" cluster. Teaching grammar is a complex and long process. When introducing new material to students, diagrams and tables should be used to facilitate understanding of information. Let's give an example of introducing the Infinitive and the Gerund.

1) "Brainstorming" method Popular verbs used by students in practice, such as to hate, to want, to like, to be, are divided into three groups:

- 1- undivided particle to,
- 2- particle without division,
3. - ing perfective verb.

2) Find sentences with these verbs from the text, explain them, translate them. This task is given to students.

Conclusion.

In order to successfully master the English language, it is suggested to follow the following methodological recommendations: It is necessary to explain language phenomena starting from the theory, basic principles, and then move on to the analysis of examples from the text or individual sentences. Give the boys the opportunity to "discover" the rule or phenomenon on their own, often with quests for exploration and ingenuity. Use a "brainstorming" method that leads them to ideas and builds on their ideas. Explain new material with the help of diagrams, tables, give logical reasoning, clear arguments. Increase boys' motivation for completed tasks, emphasize confidence in their ability to perform. performing similar tasks independently.

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